

TOPOGRAPHY OPTIMIZATION FOR MAXIMUM BUCKLING LOADS OF WIND TURBINE BLADE SANDWICH PANELS

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Finite element based topography optimization against buckling was performed on flat 19 mm thick 30 x 60 cm sandwich panels representative of wind turbine blade structures. Supported by experimental validation, results showed that optimized panels could increase buckling loads up to 27% for identical aerial mass. The ideal topography to maximize buckling load was found to be a linearly symmetric pattern oriented in the direction of loading. Although the manufacturing complexity of the optimized panel was slightly increased due to the optimized corrugated topography found, the significant increase in buckling load and decrease in core material volume leads to believe that optimized core shapes could significantly help reduce the weight of the next generation wind turbine blades.

KEYWORDS: Topography optimization, sandwich structures, buckling, wind turbine blade.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, sustainable development has been a theme well discussed around the world. With different environmental agreements established worldwide, the demand for clean energy production methods is now higher than ever. By reducing the cost of energy from 21 US\$/kWh to 3.6 US\$/kWh in the last 20 years, wind energy has become one of the most promising means of producing “green” energy of the early 21st century since it is now competitive with conventional energy production methods (gas, coal, nuclear, etc..) [1-2]. In an effort to further reduce the cost of energy, research is on going to design larger wind turbines to be operated offshore. The blades of those new wind turbines will increase significantly in size and weight making them more vulnerable to in-plane loads responsible for in-plane fatigue and trailing edge buckling.

In wind turbine blade structures like in most composite structures, one of the best ways of controlling buckling instability in regions submitted to compressive loads is to make use of sandwich constructions. On a wind turbine blade structural point of view, a large number of characteristics can influence the ability of the panel to bear the load in an efficient fashion (face sheet properties, core properties, curvature of the panel, etc...). On a manufacturing point of view, core shapes are often limited to panels of constant thickness to minimize the complexity of the blade lay-up and also because of they are used as a flow medium for the widely used infusion process. In response to the ever growing size of wind turbine blades, structural optimization efforts are now being deployed by manufacturers to minimize weight and costs of their next generation blades. This study addresses one of these structural design

issues by evaluating the potential of using optimized core shapes for wind turbine blade sandwich constructions to maximize the buckling loads while simultaneously reducing the weight. It is believed that if the optimized core shapes remain simple and allow for large areas free of core in the blade structure, significant weight reduction could be achieved without increasing blade cost. In recent years, a substantial research effort was deployed to develop different structural design optimization techniques. Topography optimization is one of them and is an advanced form of shape optimization which uses predefined shape patterns within a design region to modify grid point locations until an optimum design is reached while guided by a specific objective function. This optimization procedure was used for the production of this paper and was performed within the Hypermesh® Finite Element environment using the topography optimization tools implemented in the Optistruct® solver. Model validation of a baseline flat panel against an analytical solution and experimental results will first be addressed in this paper followed by the presentation of some promising designs and their validation.

BASELINE MODEL

Since the large size of wind turbine blades prevents experimental validation of structural design concepts by means of full scale tests, the study was conducted based on results found on substructures, namely small flat compressive test panels representative of buckling critical zones of the blade's structure. The next sections will present the characteristics and validation process of the baseline compressive panel used for comparison against the later optimized panels.

General Characteristics

To determine the general characteristics of the baseline sandwich panel to be used for comparison to the later optimized panels, representative boundary conditions, panel size, and loading were selected to realistically simulate compressive loading of wind turbine blade structures while complying with the limitations of the 1000kN compressive test bench available for testing [3]. Face sheet fiber architecture and fiber volume content was also selected to match commercial trends by choosing an orthotropic laminate configuration with a fiber volume content of 60%, placing 60% of the fibers at 0° and 40% at ±45° [4-5]. Table 1 resumes some of the other relevant panel characteristics chosen for the study.

Once the general panel characteristics determined, specimens were cut from a laminate identical to the face sheets of the sandwich panel to determine the engineering constants according to international standards. The infusion technique used for laminating these specimens was the same as the one used to manufacture the sandwich panels to be later tested therefore ensuring identical fiber volume content and mechanical properties. To determine the longitudinal compressive modulus, transverse compressive modulus and Poisson's ratios, 14 specimens were prepared and tested in compression according to the ISO 14126 standard. Similarly, complying with the ASTM

Table 1: Baseline Compressive panel general characteristics

Boundary conditions:

- Loaded end: *Clamped*
- Others: *Simply supported*

Geometric features:

- Width: *30 cm*
- Length: *60 cm*
- Face sheet thickness: *2.0 mm*
- Core thickness: *15 mm*

Materials:

- 0° fabric: Saertex Combi 1250, E-glass
- ±45 fabric: Saertex bi-axial 806, E-glass
- Core: Divinycell SG-65
- Matrix: SPsystems, Prime20

D4355 standard, the shear modulus of the face sheets was also determined. Table 2 presents the result of these experiments.

Table 2: Baseline panel face sheet and core material compressive properties

<u>Component</u>	Longitudinal Modulus E_x (GPa)	Transverse Modulus E_y (GPa)	Shear Modulus G_{xy} (GPa)	Longitudinal Poisson's Ratio ν_{xy}	Transverse Poisson's Ratio ν_{yx}
Face sheets	22.1	13.8	2.1	0.317	0.602
Core material (SG-65)	84e-3	84e-3	27e-3	-	-

Validation Process

Methodology

The validation process of the baseline compressive panel was threefold. First a finite element (FE) model of the test panel was defined with grid point locations that could later be modified to perform the topography optimization. Each adjacent cubic set of 8 nodes in the grid (58 x 61 nodes) were used to describe hexahedral solid elements to model the core material which were then covered on both sides with quadrilateral shell elements to model the orthotropic face sheets. The FE model was then completed by setting the boundary conditions to clamped edges on the loaded ends of the panel and simply supported edges on the non-loaded edges of the panel (see figure of Table 1). To complete the FE model, the engineering constants presented in Table 2 for the face sheets and core material were set as inputs respectively for the shell elements and solid elements. As a second step in the validation process, an analytical solution for flat sandwich panels was used for comparison. Numerous closed form solutions for anisotropic or orthotropic sandwich panels buckling analysis are available from literature [6-9]. Most of them are either based on energy methods or on the well documented displacement method and are solved to closed form expressions for different types of loading and boundary conditions. For their straightforwardness and simplicity, expressions presented by Zenkert [10-11] were preferred over the different analytical solutions reviewed for this project. Although only the results of the validation process will be discussed in this section, for the sake of completeness, Appendix 1 briefly presents the analytical solution favored for comparison. Finally, to correlate FE and analytical results to experimental results, buckling experiments were performed on prototype panels.

Fig. 1: Fabrication steps of the baseline compressive panels: a) The panel components are laid up, b) The panel is infused, c) After being trimmed to exact dimensions, the ends are casted using a positioning jig, c) The casted ends are finally squared to prevent parasitic bending during testing.

The production of these test panels was performed in 3 steps (see Fig. 1). First, flat panels slightly larger than the desired dimension were manufactured by vacuum infusion. Once cured, these panels were trimmed at exact dimensions taking care of leaving extra material at the loaded ends to later cast them in epoxy to simulate the clamped edges. Finally, as a final step, the loaded ends were casted and faced square to ensure that no parasitic bending could be induced when applying compressive loads.

Experimental Set-up and Results

To monitor strain during testing, 4 strain gages (SG 1,2,3 and 4 on Fig. 2a) were bonded onto the panel’s surface in the vicinity of the peaks and valleys of the 1st buckling mode estimated from the FE analysis. Two of those stain gages (SG 1 and SG 2), were positioned on opposite sides centred in the middle of the panel at 22.5cm from the base to be able to clearly detect instability and parasitic bending during loading. SG3 and SG4 were respectively position 13 cm and 26 cm above and on the same side as SG1. As a second monitoring device to detect instability and characterize the buckling mode, 3 Linear Variable Displacement Transducers (LVDT) were placed respectively at the same position as SG1, SG3 and SG1 to read lateral displacements (T1, T2 and T3 of Fig. 2b).

The three baseline panels were manufactured and loaded manually until buckling was detected while recording data points at every 2 kN. All three panels showed very similar behaviour during testing and buckled at loads of 95.9kN, 87.9kN and 88.6kN respectively. From the load-strain plot of Fig. 3, it can be noticed that parasitic bending was controlled relative well during testing since SG1 and SG2 showed quasi identical strain at low loads.

Fig. 2: Test set-up: a) side view of panel showing SG1, SG2, SG3, b) opposite side view of panel showing SG2 and the different LVDTs

Fig. 3: Test results of baseline panel #3: a) Load-Strain plot b) Load-Lateral Displacement plot

Although it was relatively difficult to visually identify the buckling mode during testing, by observing the divergence behaviour of the different strain gages it can be concluded that it is most probable that the panel buckled in a single wave mode shape since the type of divergence of SG2 and SG4 suggests that they are positioned in valleys (increase negative strain) while SG1 and SG3 are positioned on peaks (reduction of negative strain). This is in agreement with Fig.3b that shows that the lateral displacement of transducers 2 and 3 (T2 and T3) positioned right over strain gages SG1 and SG3 detected increasing negative values while transducers T1 read positive values at first and finally read negative values when approaching the buckling load.

Finite Element and Analytical Solution Comparison

Using the Optistruct[®] solver of Altair's[®] Hypermesh[®] FE packages, the Lanczos method was employed to extract the eigenvalues of the baseline panel. The results of the first 3 eigenvalues buckling loads are shown in Fig. 4 with the corresponding deformed grid of mode 1. When compared to the experimental results, the FE method underestimated the critical buckling load by 2.4% on average. Recalling that the experimental lateral displacements read by all transducers were negative, it can be concluded from Fig. 4 that the 1st mode shape found with the FE analysis was not reproduced physically during the experiments. Since it is very difficult to identify complex mode shapes experimentally with only 3 control points, it is impossible to tell if the panel actually buckled at a higher mode shape or simply suffered from Euler buckling due to the lack of rigidity of the guide rails used to simulate the simple supported edges. Nevertheless, this experimental validation against FE results showed that buckling loads could be estimated with sufficient accuracy to rely on the optimized topography later found with the OptistructTM FE solver.

Buckling load:

1st mode: 88.6 kN

2nd mode: 88.9 kN

3rd mode: 91.6 kN

Fig. 4: First three eigenvalue buckling loads with first mode shape of the baseline panel.

When using the analytical expressions presented in Appendix 1, the buckling load was found to be overestimated by 42% compared to the experimental results. As observed by Zenkert [10,11] and Whitney [6], analytical expressions derived from an approximated deflected field function can yield significant errors if their aspect ratio (a/b) and/or degree of orthotropic (D_x/D_y) don't stay within a specific range. For the deflection field expression presented in Eqn. 7, Zenkert predicted an accuracy within 15 to 20% if $0.7 < [(b/a)(D_x/D_y)^{1/4}] < 1.4$. One of the probable explanations to this overestimation could be due to the relatively high degree of orthotropy of the panel's face sheets combined with a low b/a ratio which forced the lower bound of this validity expression to be exceeded (0.59). Furthermore, Zenkert showed that panels with relatively low core shear stiffness (S_x) like the one used in this study were prone to a lower degree of accuracy. These two possible sources of error combined could explain the significant overestimation experienced with the analytical solution.

OPTIMIZED MODEL

In topography optimization of wind turbine blade sandwich panels, since the geometry of the outer face sheet of blades must comply with the local airfoil geometry, only the topography of the inner face sheet should be allowed to be modified to yield optimum solutions. Following this approach, to optimize the panel against buckling the objective function should be set to

maximize the lowest eigen buckling frequency of the most critical buckling modes (usually the first 3 or 4 are sufficient). To prevent the panel to increase in thickness but only decrease during the optimization process, a constraint should be applied on the objective function in the form of bounds on grid point displacements, i.e, increasing out-of-plane displacements of the face sheet grid points from the baseline thickness of the panel should not be permitted while a free displacement towards the inside of the panel should be allowed up to a maximum value equal to the original core thickness to prevent the solid elements used to model the core to be turned inside out. Finally, to keep the optimum solutions to a low degree of complexity, manufacturing constraints should be applied during the optimization process to force some symmetry patterns. In early stages of the project it became evident that the big drawback of using this approach would be the inability of the model to locally stiffen the displacement between nodes that would eventually be touching each other during the optimization process (locally reconnected face sheets). Since a significant part of the resistance of sandwich panels against buckling can come from the shear properties of the core material, especially for low shear stiffness core material panels, a significant increase in buckling load can be obtained from reconnecting face sheets in strategic areas. Monolithic corrugated panels with one or two flat face sheets are great examples of an optimum design using this type of in-plane shear locking. Unfortunately, within a FE based optimization process, constraining displacements between nodes at specific iterations is not an option since it would create discontinuity jumps in the objective function. To circumvent this difficulty, the optimization process was segmented in three steps:

- First gain incite on the most probable optimum topographies by studying a face sheet alone.
- From these topography results, select a series of adjacent nodes where both face sheets should be reconnected prior to optimization.
- Perform the final topography optimization on the full panel with these predetermined stiffened areas.

This optimization procedure was performed within the Hypermesh® finite element environment using the topography optimization tools implemented in the Optistruct® solver.

Results

As a first step in the optimization process, different symmetry pattern groupings were tested on a single face sheet to gain incite on promising topographies. Contrary to classic optimization problems in which symmetry patterns usually reduces the performance, by carefully selecting symmetry patterns it was showed that it was possible to obtain far more optimized solutions than while leaving the optimization be performed without symmetry constraints. Figure 5 depicts some of the symmetry patterns tested with their corresponding improvement compared to the non-constrained solution.

Fig. 5: Topography plots showing the effect of different pattern grouping on buckling loads (P): a) Unconstrained, b) 2-plane symmetry, c) Linear pattern (extrusion).

It was found that on a topography optimization level, corrugated topographies found with linearly symmetric patterns are best suited to maximize the buckling load. They are also very simple to manufacture which makes them appealing compared to other solutions.

In a second step, based on the 1-plane symmetry pattern grouping results, a FE model was set up to be used with adjacent linear sets of nodes on both skins rigidly connected to each other. This model was then used to yield optimum corrugated topographies with an optimization scheme similar to the one previously discussed. In this case, starting with both skins very close together, the objective function was set to maximize the buckling load by modifying the out-of-plane grid point location of one skin while being constrained by an upper bound of 15 mm to limit the panel thickness to the thickness of the baseline panel. The other skin was not included in the design domain and was therefore left flat. To see the effect of using different corrugated pattern density across the panel's surface, optimization runs were tried with 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6 rigidly connected node sets along the panel length. Using a second constraint to control possible fiber bridging during manufacturing, the optimization process was also restrained by a maximum corrugated pattern angle of 60°. Results presented in Fig. 6 show that the different optimized corrugated panels were able to yield up to 27% higher buckling loads for quasi-equivalent panel mass. To validate experimentally these results, 3 panels using a pattern wave length of 30 cm were manufactured and tested in an identical fashion than previously presented. As with the baseline panel compressive test, buckling critical loads were reproduced reasonably well since an average error of 9% was found when compared to the FE results. Unfortunately, as it was the case with the baseline panel, mode shapes were not recaptured experimentally.

<u>Cross-section shape</u>	<u>Pattern wave length (cm)</u>	<u>Buckling load (kN)</u>		<u>Mass (g)</u>	
		<i>FEM</i>	<i>Experimental</i>	<i>Estimated</i>	<i>Measured</i>
	-	88.6	95.9/87.9/88.6	1693.3	1701 (av.)
	30	98.6	108/104/111	1663.3	1675 (av.)
	15	111.0	-	1707.2	-
	10	111.9	-	1714.3	-
	7.5	106.1	-	1722.0	-
	6	99.4	-	1728.8	-

Fig. 6: Buckling loads and corresponding masses of linearly symmetric optimized 15 mm thick panels for different corrugated pattern densities. The first line shows the baseline flat panel results for comparison.

CONCLUSION

Although experimental results showed that the critical buckling load could be accurately predicted with FE analysis for both the baseline panel and one of the optimized panels, mode shapes were in all cases difficult to predict using the experimental set-up described earlier. Future work is planned in that respect to improve on the method by using more monitoring points, test new guide rails for simply supported edges and possibly use Moiré patterns to visually characterize the mode shapes.

Results showed that by using FE based topography optimisation tools wind turbine blade sandwich structures could be optimized to provide a 27% increase in buckling load without increasing the panel's aerial mass. This increase in buckling load was found with forced linearly symmetric patterns that proved to be best suited for sandwich panels submitted to uniaxial in-plane loading. Using geometric characteristics specific to this study, corrugated patterns with wave lengths of 10cm and 15cm showed the highest buckling load while still

being comparable in mass to the baseline flat panel. Although not studied in this work, the increase in manufacturing costs due to the presence of a more complex core shape should not be significant since the topographies found are of the simplest form possible.

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APPENDIX

Analytical solution for orthotropic sandwich panels

The most general state of stress a panel can be subjected to is illustrated in fig. A1 where variables M , N , T and q are respectively bending moments, normal forces, transverse forces and uniform transverse pressure. In the case where the only existing load is N_x , the governing equations based on strain and potential energy principle can be reduced to Eqn. 1 in which w is the lateral deflexion field of the panel in the x and y plane with w_b and w_s being respectively the bending and shear components. For orthotropic sandwich panels, assuming identical face sheets and a weak core compared to the face sheets, the flexural rigidities D_x and D_y and the twisting rigidity D_{xy} can be respectively approximated with Eqn. 2, 3 and 4, where the modulus are those of the face sheets, t is the face sheet thickness, and d is the distance between the centroide of the face sheets ($t_{core} + t_{face_sheet}$).

Fig. A1: General loading state of a panel of width b , length a , and thickness t .

$$U_p = \frac{1}{2} \iint N_x \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right)^2 dx dy \quad U_s = \frac{1}{2} \iint \left[\frac{D_x}{1 - \nu_{xy}\nu_{yx}} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w_b}{\partial x^2} \right)^2 + \frac{\nu_{yx}D_x + \nu_{xy}D_y}{1 - \nu_{xy}\nu_{yx}} + 2D_{xy} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w_b}{\partial x^2} \right) \left(\frac{\partial^2 w_b}{\partial y^2} \right) + \frac{D_y}{1 - \nu_{xy}\nu_{yx}} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w_b}{\partial y^2} \right)^2 + 2D_{xy} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w_b}{\partial x \partial y} \right)^2 + S_x \left(\frac{\partial w_s}{\partial x} \right)^2 + S_y \left(\frac{\partial w_s}{\partial y} \right)^2 \right] dx dy \quad (1)$$

$$D_x \approx \frac{E_x t d^2}{2} \quad (2) \quad D_y \approx \frac{E_y t d^2}{2} \quad (3) \quad D_{xy} \approx G_{xy} t d^2 \quad (4) \quad S_x \approx \frac{G_{cx} d^2}{t_c} \quad (5) \quad S_y \approx \frac{G_{cy} d^2}{t_c} \quad (6)$$

As with any other attempt in finding a closed form expression for critical buckling load of a panel constrained by specific boundary conditions, the difficulty in solving Eqn. 1 lies in finding a suitable function for w that represents accurately the mode shape of the panel. The most common practice is to use sinusoidal functions. While exact functions can be expressed for cases where all edges are being simply supported (double Fourier sine series are commonly used), an accepted practice for cases with more complex boundary conditions is to approximate w with a sinusoidal function of only one coefficient. In the case of a panel being clamped on loaded ends and having simply supported edges, the function used with corresponding boundary conditions can be expressed as:

$$w = w_b + w_s = (\bar{w}_b + \bar{w}_s) \sin \frac{\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{m\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{\pi y}{b}, \quad \begin{cases} \text{when } x = 0, a \rightarrow w = 0 \text{ and } \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} = 0 \\ \text{when } y = 0, b \rightarrow w = 0 \text{ and } \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Using the Ritz' method, the approximated amplitude function \bar{w} ($\bar{w} = \bar{w}_b + \bar{w}_s$) to minimize the total energy (strain + potential) can be found to be:

$$\bar{w} = \frac{16qb^4(1 - \nu_{xy}\nu_{yx})}{\pi^5 \left[16D_x \left(\frac{b}{a} \right)^4 + 8 \left[D_x \nu_{yx} + (1 - \nu_{xy}\nu_{yx}) D_{xy} \right] \left(\frac{b}{a} \right)^2 + 3D_y \right]} + \frac{16qb^2}{\pi^3 \left[16S_x \left(\frac{b}{a} \right)^2 + 3S_y \right]} \quad (8)$$

When replaced in the governing equation, a closed form solution for the buckling load can be expressed as:

$$\frac{1}{P} = \frac{4b^2(1-\nu_{xy}\nu_{yx})}{\pi^2 \left[16D_x \left(\frac{b}{a} \right)^2 + 3D_y \left(\frac{a}{b} \right)^2 + 8 \left[\nu_{yx} D_x + D_{xy} (1-\nu_{xy}\nu_{yx}) \right] \right]} + \frac{1}{S_x + \frac{3S_y}{4} \left(\frac{a}{b} \right)^2} \quad (9)$$

for $m = 1$, and

$$\frac{1}{P} = \frac{A_m b^2 (1-\nu_{xy}\nu_{yx})}{\pi^2 \left[D_x B_m \left(\frac{b}{a} \right)^2 + D_y \left(\frac{a}{b} \right)^2 + 2A_m \left[\nu_{yx} D_x + D_{xy} (1-\nu_{xy}\nu_{yx}) \right] \right]} + \frac{A_m}{S_x A_m + S_y \left(\frac{a}{b} \right)^2} \quad (10)$$

when $m > 1$, where $A_m = (1+m^2)$ and $B_m = (m^4+6m^2+1)$. The minimum buckling load will correspond to the minimum value of P for integer values of m . Computing for the engineering constant presented in Table 1, a minimum buckling load of 128 kN was found for the baseline panel.